

No.	Molecular formula	M. P.* °C	Yield %	%C		%H		%I	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
I	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂	241	21.7	78.86	78.89	4.955	4.498	—	—
II	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂ I	205	59	—	—	—	—	30.105	30.51
III	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂ I ₂	230	70.5	—	—	—	—	46.238	46.65
IV	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₂	173-74	80	43.01	43.24	2.548	2.34	45.62	45.76
V	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₂	207	80	76.07	76.14	4.408	4.532	—	—

*All the m. p. s are uncorrected.

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Terpenoids. Part: CVI. A New Synthesis of 2E,6-Farnesol

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RECENTLY γ -carbon alkylation of β -ketoesters has attracted the attention of synthetic organic chemists because of their potential applications in organic synthesis¹⁻³. We have already reported the syntheses of some terpenoids^{3,4} utilizing this elegant technique. In this communication, we wish to report, based on the same approach, a new synthesis of 2E, 6-farnesol, an acyclic sesquiterpenoid alcohol, isolated from *Abelmoschus moschatus* Moensch and from other essential oils⁵. Structure (1) has been established on the basis of physical and chemical properties⁶ and syntheses⁷⁻⁹. The sequence of the reactions leading to the synthesis of title compound is given in chart 1.

β -Ketoester (II), obtained by selective alkylation of the dianion from acetoacetic ester³, with geranyl bromide, was converted into the chloride (III) in 65% yield with PCl₅ in chloroform. Chloroester (III) was reacted with lithiumdimethyl copper reagent¹⁰ to furnish, α - β unsaturated ester (IV) in 55% yield. The resulting product was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina when elution with petroleum : benzene (4 : 1) gave (IV). The purity of the compound (IV) was checked by TLC which showed a single spot (ether benzene : 4 : 1). The formation of *trans* product was confirmed through NMR spectrum

which showed signals at τ : 8.85 (3H, t, $\text{—C—O—CH}_2\text{—CH}_3$), 8.3–8.5 (9H, q, allylic methyl), 7.8–8.1 (11H, q, 8H allylic methylene and 3H, —CH_3 *cis* to $\text{—CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$) and 4.7–5.1 (3H, m, olefinic protons).

Allylic methyl formed by the reaction of lithium dimethyl copper reagent on (III) is deshielded because of which it displays the singlet in the region where the allylic methylene protons exhibit the signals, thereby proving beyond doubt that $\text{—CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ is *cis* to —CH_3 and hence *trans* to the big group. Our results are consistent which those reported in lit.¹¹ Casey *et al* have observed that β -Ketoester when converted into the acetate in acidic conditions followed by lithium copper dimethyl reagent gave *trans*-product.

Finally, α - β -unsaturated ester (IV) on reduction with LAH in benzene¹² afforded 2E, 6-farnesol (1). The identity of the synthetic alcohol was established by

comparing its spectral characteristics with those of authentic sample, reported in lit.⁸

Experimental

B. ps. are uncorrected. IR spectra (thin films) were recorded on a Perkin Elmer infrared spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded at 60 MHz using TMS as an internal reference in CCl_4 as solvent.

Ethyl 7, 11-dimethyl-3-oxo-6, 10-dodecadienoate (II). This was obtained exactly according to the procedure laid down in lit.⁹

Ethyl 7, 11-dimethyl-3-chloro-2, 6, 10-dodecatrienoate (III). The compound (II, 7.9 g) was added dropwise with stirring to the solution of PCl_5 (2.8 g) in dry chloroform (40 ml.). The stirring was continued for 4 hr. and it was left overnight. The contents were decomposed with cold water, the organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was dried and the solvent was expelled under reduced pressure furnishing the chloride (III, 5.45 g) in 65% yield; ν_{max} 1710, 1620, 1460, 1310, 1233, 1170, 1140, 1120, and 767 cm^{-1} , (Found: C, 67.61; H, 8.72%; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_2$ Cl. requires C, 67.55; H, 8.80%;)

Ethyl 3, 7, 10-trimethyl 2E, 6, 10-dodecatrienoate (IV). To the solution of the reagent in ether, prepared from the reaction of methyl-lithium (237 ml., 1.34N) in ether with cuprous iodide (26.6 g) molar ratio 2 : 1, at 0° under nitrogen atmosphere, was added slowly the compound (III, 9 g). The stirring was continued for 4 hr. and it was left overnight. The contents were decomposed with cold water and product was extracted with ether and ether extract was dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue after solvent evaporation was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina using pet. ether : benzene (4 : 1) as eluent, providing (IV, 4.55g) in 55% yield; ν_{max} 1715, 1115, 1020 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$). (Found: C, 77.10; H, 10.58. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.22; H, 10.67%).

3,7,10-Trimethyl -2E, 6, 10-dodecatrienol (I). To a fine suspension of LAH (420 mg) in benzene (50 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of ester (IV, 2.4 g) in benzene (20 ml.) maintaining the temp. at 60°. The contents were further stirred for 8 hr at 60°. After usual work up and distillation under reduced pressure it afforded (I, 1.3 g.) in 60% yield; ν_{max} 3450, 1630, 1395, 1350, 1110, 1015, 970, 840 and 810 cm^{-1} . NMR (60MHz CCl_4) spectrum showed signals at τ : 8.3–8.42 (9H,m, allylic methyl), 7.92–8.1 (1H,m, allylic methylene and $-\text{CH}_3$ at C_2), 5.9 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) and 4.6–5.0 (3H,m, vinylic protons). (Found: C, 84.71; H, 7.55. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.87; H, 7.60%).

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Constituents of the Roots of *Selinum papyraceum*

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ONLY three species of *Selinum* (Umbelliferae), *S. vaginatum*^{1,2}, *S. tenuifolium*³, and *S. monnieri*⁴ have been chemically investigated so far for coumarins. In view of this it was thought desirable to undertake a chemical investigation on another *Selinum* species, viz. *S. papyraceum* C. B. Clarke.

Dried and powdered roots of *S. papyraceum* (collected from the Eastern Himalayas) were extracted with petrol (b. p. 60°-80°) for 20 hr. The extract showed at least six u. v. fluorescent spots on TLC. The residue from the petrol extract was chromatographed on silica gel. No crystalline product could be isolated from petrol and petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluates,

Fractions from benzene eluates were combined (on the basis of TLC pattern) and rechromatographed on silica gel. Solvent was removed from the first fractions and the residue crystallised from methanol to give sitosterol, m.p. 137° (positive Lieberman-Burchard test, Co, TLC, m.m.p., acetate, m.p. 129°).

Further elution with benzene gave fractions showing three spots on TLC. Preparative TLC on silica gel G using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as the solvent afforded a product in small yields. It melted at 116°-117° and showed pale brown u. v. fluorescence. IR and NMR data revealed the identity of the product with knidilin (I)⁵.